
Working With Problems an Innovation in Teaching Programming Languages

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Abstract

Teaching any programming language requires high level of teaching skills. The teacher needs to have an in depth knowledge in the programming language. In addition to this he or she needs to develop many projects using the programming language before teaching. Today it has become a common practice in teaching environment that the teacher is giving more and more responsibilities to the programming language and the instructions and syntax than the actual implementations of the language. Today it's a common practice that the students find it difficult in developing any project using the skills and knowledge which he or she has learnt inside the class room. This is because every student is failing in working with the problems. The students fail in developing the logic before using any programming language for implementation. This paper introduces the new methodology to be adopted in teaching where all the students are active throughout the working hour. The model introduced here concentrates on the teaching faculty working more and more on problems than the solutions. This model forces the students to rigorously think on the solutions for the problems given by the teachers. This develops the thinking power of students and hence they will be able to work with the real time problems in the IT industries.

Keywords: *teaching environment, programming language, problem domain, methodology, programming logic*

1. Introduction

The ancient Indian education system was Gurukula based system where the teacher who was acting like a teacher as well as a parent.[1] The aspirant who is also called the student should go to such Gurukula at the tender age of seven years leaving his parental affections. He had to learn for minimum of eighteen years to attain knowledge both theoretically as well as practically.[2] The teacher used to teach a student with all possible knowledge. He used to give more and more importance to practical aspects of the knowledge in order to make the student not only understand the concepts theoretically but also practically. In Gurukula system every student had to learn the basic discipline, living togetherness, simplicity and other human values along with study. The student might be from a rich background, son of a king, poor background or what ever was equally treated by the teachers.

Present day education system is the classroom based education system where both teaching domain and learning domain sit and discuss the subject for a period of six to eight hours a day.

After the school hours both the domains will be engaged with other work [3]. The teaching learning process functions only one third of a day which is not at all sufficient for the learning domain. More over this system diverts the interest of the learning domain to some other fields which may be harmful to the learning environment[4]. Learning is a continuous activity for a student who is in the learning domain.

Teaching a programming language needs additional skills for the teaching domain [5]. In the case of programming language the knowledge of the teaching domain may be at a very high level as the domain might have worked in the programming language from years together. While teaching this subject the teaching domain thinks that the learning domain has some knowledge about the subject. But the learning domain will not have any subject background so that the resultant of which is there will not be a synchronization between teaching and learning domain inside the class [6].

The teaching domain in order to deliver the knowledge tries its level best in attracting the attention of the learning domain. Here one major possibility is the teaching domain remains in unidirectional way delivering lecture without thinking what is the reaction of the learning domain [7]. It is very clear from the student psychology that a student can not concentrate for more than one hour if he is not given any activities [8].

The programming language is understood by the learning domain only when the domain applies the programming language technique to solve the problems. Today the learning domain finds it very difficult to develop the logic for solving the problems [9]. This might be due to the detailed unidirectional discussion of the subject by the teaching domain. The learning domain does not even try to develop the logic because the logic and a program code for solving a problem is discussed by the teaching domain. Due to this the developing skill for the learning domain remains unsatisfied. This scenario makes the learning domain feel uncomfortable inside the classroom because no mental work is given, no activity is discussed which make the learning domain active throughout the session [10].

It is very true that the learning domain is very much interested with modern electronic devices like smart phones, tablets and other Internet applications [11] . It is very true that the teaching domain finds it difficult to work with such latest technologies than the learning domain. From this it is very clear that the learning domain is no longer weak in studies but lack of interest in studies make that domain to suffer from getting distinction in the core subject. The in depth knowledge in such latest technology is only due to the interest of the learning domain. The domain struggles a lot to get the training but does not stop until the new knowledge is achieved [12]. Today the teaching domain instead of encouraging such technology and using such technology towards learning the subject, demotivate the learning domain from using the smart phone technology.

2. Objective of the paper:

- To maintain the students in active learning mode throughout the period.
- To maintain the teacher in problem domain than solution domain.
- To convert the student interests to learning environment.

3. Methodology:

It's quite common that students do not concentrate on the subject if they don't like it or understand it. This makes a teacher to face a challenge to get interest in the students towards the subject. During the teaching session the teacher has to keep the students interested towards

the subject. Teacher can engage the students only when the students start thinking about the solutions to the problems related to the subject. Here the teacher has to explain the concept of the subject in detail. Then the teacher based on the concept should give as many problems as possible to the students. In order to solve the problems the students always remain active. Hence the learning domain gets more knowledge. The proposed model is as shown in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Proposed teaching learning model.

This figure is very clear in keeping the teacher in the problem domain rather in the solution domain. The present teaching method concentrates on teaching the logic of the program and the program code in detail. This does not give the exercise to the learner's mind. The effect of this is the learning domain cannot independently solve the problems. Here the teaching domain should teach the various instructions, special features of the programming language so that the learning domain should use the same features of the programming language to develop a program. This effort of the learning domain in self programming a given problem develops a self-confidence and is useful in the future when developing the big software projects. Use of mobile apps should be more and more entertained as the learning domain is more and more attracted towards mobile apps. This helps in gaining more concentration in problem solving by the learning domain.

Here the teaching domain has the following responsibilities

- Deep discussion of the theory of the programming language.
- Brief discussion about the logic of any program
- Monitoring the learning domain in adopting the skills in developing the program/logic
- Timely suggestion while learning domain solves the problem.
- Use of Mobile Apps should be entertained.

This model strongly support the use of smart phones inside the classroom. Use of smart phones inside the classroom has two major advantages. They are

- Use of relevant apps from the smart phone help them to learn the programming concept as well as increases the confidence level for developing the logic.
- Avoids the misuse of the smart phone inside the class as the phone is busy with the learning domain in solving the problem using the relevant apps.

4. ABCD analysis of the model:

4.1 Advantages of using this model

This model is very much useful in Teaching Learning environment as the learning environment is actively participating in the session. The model encourages more and more on problem solving by the learning domain using the programming language that the teacher is teaching. Use of Mobile apps increases the interest in the learning domain.

4.2 Benefits of using this model

By using this model the teaching domain gets complete satisfaction because the learning domain is understanding the entire subject thoroughly. The main objective of the teaching domain is achieved from this. By using this model the teaching and learning domains can come out with new innovative ideas. These innovative ideas will enhance the knowledge of teaching domain.

4.3 Constraints for using this model

It is difficult to practice this model in the current environment. The classroom based teaching having more than fifty students in a class is one of the constraints. The syllabus for a teaching domain per semester restricts the application of this model in teaching.

4.4 Drawbacks of using this model

This model is helpful for such domain where the learning domain should be ready to accept. Today the learning domain except for few do not have the goal set. For such domain this model is difficult to apply. The time restriction for completing the syllabus for the teaching domain is another drawback.

5. Conclusion

The above said model is suitable in developing the reasoning, logical thinking, working on innovative ideas for the learning domain. But the teaching and learning domain should not function with time restriction. If a learning domain grasps the idea fast then he or she will be completing the course early than the slow learners. Today our teaching learning system is totally time bound where in both the slow and fast learners should complete the degree in same time. In such condition the fast learners complete the degree whereas the slow learners fail to complete the degree. The teaching and learning domain should not restrict to the time bound. The teacher can the student to next level only when he or she deserves. This results in more and more hard work in the student domain.

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